

Characteristics of children with ASD attending Inclusive Education and its Association with Social Skills: A survey

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Abstract

Objectives: This study understands the differences in inclusion and social skills among children with autism spectrum disorder (ASD). In order to investigate these differences, social skills were associated with characteristics of these children like age, gender, etc.

Methods: For the purposes of the study a total of 395 parents of children with ASD were selected in Delhi NCR. Inclusion Survey and SRS-2 was used.

Results: The results showed the inclusivity of child with ASD. And showed that the score of severity score is significantly different for those who received social skills training programs for different symptom domains of SRS scale.

Conclusion: Social skills training program has influence on scores for SRS scale in children with ASD. Social skills can increase inclusivity in children with ASD.

Keywords: Inclusion, social skills, students with ASD.

Introduction

Social skills and Inclusion

Why are social skills important for inclusion of social skills improve by Social cognition, social skill, and social motivation have been extensively researched and characterised as atypical in autistic people, with the assumption that each mechanistically contributes to the broader social interaction difficulties that diagnostically define the condition. Despite this assumption, research has not directly assessed whether or how these three social domains contribute to actual real-world social interaction outcomes for autistic people.

When considering a systemic approach to social competencies, the development of necessary social skills should be an essential part of the educational curriculum to support the functioning of all students within the school, family, and wider socio-ecological systems (AACTE, 2010).

There is a need to explore various factors and include parents' perspectives to describe and and correlate various determinants of social inclusion. Hence, due to limited information in these areas, the focus of the research is to study.

Social inclusion

Social inclusion or “feeling like an integrated member of society, enjoying needed support from others, and participating in normal community activities with other people” (Schalock and Verdugo 2002).

Inclusive Education

Education is a human right of every child whether she/he is disabled or non-disabled. In order to make education for all a reality, every child must have access to quality education (Limaye, 2016). The UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (2006) ratified by India prohibits

any sort of exclusion from educational opportunities on the basis of abilities. The Inclusive model of education ensures full participation in regular education classrooms by facilitating access to the general education curriculum to their full learning potential (Sharma & Forlin, 2012; Hettiarachchi & Das, 2014; Shah, Das, Desai, & Tiwari, 2014).

Since ASD is a very heterogeneous disorder, various factors might be at play when looking at a good fit to achieve positive outcomes of inclusive education (Cathy Little 2017; Kirkovski et al, 2013; Tager Flusberg and Joseph, 2003).

Previous research studies have shown a difference between the behavioral profiles associated with social acceptance and rejection for students with Moderate Learning Disabilities and mainstream students (Frederickson and Furnham, 2004).

In many schools across India, children with ASD attending school settings spend the majority of their instructional day with special education teachers in a pullout classroom (Parasuram 2006). However, in developing countries like India, children with ASD show apparently more social deficits in inclusive settings to the extent of experiencing social rejection and bullying (Begara et al 2019). Thus, it stands to reason that developing understanding and awareness as part of Social Skills of ASD would increase empathy and thus facilitate inclusion and positive interactions between children with ASD and their peers (Lidija Balaz et al, 2020).

Along with benefits, several challenges related to inclusive education also go hand in hand. The greatest barrier is the negative attitude of society towards it. There are obstacles in the form of physical barriers, the inability of the curriculum to meet the needs of a wide range of learners, and the lack of adequate training for staff (Mieghaem et.al, 2020; Sharma and Mahapatra 2007). Benefits of inclusive education may be reduced for children with Autism as difficulty in learning through social interaction with peers and teachers is a core challenge of their nature of disability leading to exclusion (Pimentel-Camargo et al 2014).

Thus, the conceptual understanding and implementation of Inclusion in India differs vastly from that in western developed nations such as the US and UK. Inclusion in India needs to be studied to gain insights on the current state of things and to find out what are the determinants of Social Inclusion.

Social skills and Inclusion

Social cognition, social skill, and social motivation have been extensively researched and characterised as atypical in autistic people, with the assumption that each mechanistically contributes to the broader social interaction difficulties that diagnostically define the condition. Despite this assumption, research has not directly assessed whether or how these three social domains contribute to actual real-world social interaction outcomes for autistic people.

There is a need to explore various factors and include parents' perspectives to describe and correlate various determinants of social inclusion. Hence, due to limited information in these areas, the focus of the research is to study them.

Methodology**Aim**

The aim of this research was to find the determinants of inclusion for children with ASD. For this study, the data was collected from parents of children with ASD.

Objectives

This study understands the differences in inclusion and social skills among children with autism spectrum disorder (ASD). In order to investigate these differences, social skills were associated with characteristics of these children like age.

Research Question

What is the inclusion of children with ASD?

What is the association of Social skills with different characteristics of children with ASD?

Hypothesis

It was hypothesised that there will be a significant relationship between the characteristics of children with ASD and their social skills when participating in inclusive setup.

ADDED

The score of Social Responsiveness is different for children who attended and did not attend inclusive education.

The score of Social Responsiveness symptom domain is different for children with social skills program.

Research Design

Survey Design was used wherein parents also responded about their participation in the inclusion set up using the Social Inclusion and Support Survey. The parent participants also responded about the social skills of their child with ASD using the standardised tool, Social Responsiveness Scale-Second Edition by John N. Constantino, MD, 2019.

Sample

Type of sampling technique

Non probability, convenience sampling was used; participants were recruited simply by connecting with parents that are regularly visiting to access therapy for their children. Some participants were connected through social media networks.

Sample Size

For this study a total number of 395 parents of children, with 299 males (75 %) and 96 females. Out of the sample 151 children attended preschool, 122 children attended school and 122 children did not attend any school. The research was done at multiple therapy centres of Delhi NCR, both online and offline. For the purpose of this study, only those parents were involved whose children were aged between 2.5 to 14 years. All the participants were on a voluntary basis.

Inclusion, exclusion criteria

We have included children whose parents are from varied educational, ethnic, financial backgrounds but only those that have attended and participated in Indian inclusive settings of Delhi/ NCR.

Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Children clinically diagnosed with ASD ● Age range of children were 2.5- 14 years ● Children who attended inclusive setting for any period of time ● Children who did not attend inclusive school ● Children of any gender 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Children with autism with co-existing conditions such as seizures, deafness, blindness etc. ● Children residing out of Delhi NCR. ● Children who were exposed to inclusive settings outside India. ● Non-resident Children who were travelling to India for therapy.

Tools and Instruments

Social Responsiveness Scale

Standardized tool, Social Responsiveness Scale, Second Edition (SRS-2) by John N. Constantino, MD, 2019 was used. The SRS2 incorporates first hand ratings from individuals (parents, teachers, spouses) who have observed the individual in naturalistic settings and requires 15 – 20 minutes. The test measures the social ability of children from 2.5 years to 18 years old. SRS – 2 was used as “The SRS 2 offers specific advantages over existing autism rating scales. These include the ability to quantify subtle differences in degree of impairment, strong reliability across various informants, stability, or inter individual differences over years of time” (Constantino et. al, 2009). This study used 2 out of four versions that were available, each with 65 items: school-age (ages 4 - 18 years), preschool (ages 2.5 - 4.5 years). The questionnaire SRS-2 assesses the children under 5 domains: Social Communication, Social Cognition, Social Motivation, Social Communication and Interest, and Restricted Repetitive Behaviour. SRS-2 is distinct from other measures as it provides a

continuous measure of social skills ranging from impaired to above average instead of a categorical yes/no identification of ASD impairments. The questionnaire should be given and interpreted by someone who has sufficient expertise in the treatment of individuals with ASD and the use of psychological tests and assessments (Constantino JN, Gruber CP, 2012). The SRS-2 unlimited-use scoring tool generates a complete report with descriptive information that may be used to guide intervention.

Higher SRS scores represent more ASD-related behaviors. We used a cutoff T score of 60 as an indication of mild to moderate risk for ASD for this analysis. This cutoff results in a 96.8% likelihood of a later clinical diagnosis of ASD (Constantino et al. 2007). Although Schanding et al. (2012) did explore optimal cut offs for the SRS, this study's sample had a very large age range. Therefore, we explored only the cut off reported in the manual in the current analysis.

Previous research also suggests that the SRS could be a cost-effective assessment for measuring ASD symptoms in school and clinical settings. Specifically, the SRS has been found to be useful at differentiating between children with ASD and those without ASD (Cholemkery et al. 2014; Wang et al. 2012).

Designing the Social Inclusion and Support Survey

Survey was designed with the goal of studying the social inclusion of children with autism spectrum disorder (ASD) in school settings in India. The existing literature guided framing of items, choosing syntax of items. The Social Inclusion and Support survey consisted of closed ended questions as they were deemed easier to deal with. The closed ended questions included a mix of general information questions, categorical questions, and continuous data about attending inclusive settings. The survey was divided into 3 sections where a total of 24 questions were used. Section A has 10 general data questions, Section B has 3 clinical data questions and Section C has 11 inclusion related questions. In Section C there were 4 'Yes' and 'No' questions; 1 was a multiple choice question.

Content Validity

The capacity of the selected items to represent the construct variables in the measure is referred to as content validity. This sort of validity is concerned with the extent to which an instrument's items adequately represent the content domain.

Three subject experts were chosen based on their specialty and in-depth knowledge of the subject for their expert feedback and were approached for item relevance evaluations.

After receiving expert replies, we went through their suggestions, integrated them, and created a final version of the questionnaire.

The following are the items related to Inclusion

Q1.	To date, how many years/ months has your child attended any school/ classroom (Duration in months)?	
Q2.	Did your child attend inclusive school/ classroom (Y/N)?	
Q3.	How many hours per week did he attend?	
Q4.	Was there a provision of pull-out therapy during the inclusive school (Y/N)?	
Q5.	How many hours per week did he attend any pull out therapy during the inclusive school?	
Q6.	To date, how many months has your child attended therapy Services (Duration in months)?	
Q7.	Did your child attend any after school therapy while the child attended inclusive school (Y/N)?	
Q8.	How many hours per week of after school therapy did he attend?	
Q9.	Did he attend any social skills program either at school or during after school therapy (Y/N)?	
Q10.	How many hours per week did he/ she attend the social skills group program?	
Q11.	In your view what affects inclusion of your child most (choose one): a) Behavior b) Speech c) Social Skills d) Pre-academic /Academic e) Self Help skills f) Playing Skills g) Paying attention skills	

PROCEDURE

Administering the survey

In order to include as many participants as possible the researcher used all possible ways of meeting face-to-face, mailing questionnaires, peer dissemination, telephone and email as per convenience. Database was created by approaching different centers and e-mails were sent to more than 1000 parents of children with autism. The questionnaire was converted to a google form and disseminated.-Reminders were also sent to respond.

Consent and debriefing

Written / oral voluntary consent for participation was taken from each participant. Ethical clearance was obtained by the Institutional Review Board of IILM University.

Statistical Analysis

Statistical analysis of the data was performed using the standard statistical package for the social sciences (SPSS, version 22). Also, descriptive statistics, content validity was done. Additionally, correlation and t-test was applied in order to conduct comparisons and associations, to analyze the differences among group means and to examine the influence of the variables on the factors of ASD children

Coding categorical data

All the data for quantitative analysis should, with a few exceptions, be recorded using numerical codes. The survey data was entered using the SPSS software.

Analysis

Demographic characteristics of children with ASD				
Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)	Mean	SD
Gender				
Male	299	75.69	-	-
Female	95	24.31	-	-
Age (in months)				
29 - 60	108		-	-
60 - 90	143		-	-
90 - 120	83		-	-
120 - 150	45		-	-
150 - 180	16		-	-
School/ Grade Level				
Preschool	151	38.22	85.622	36.616
School	122	30.88	86.473	36.724
Not attending	122	30.88	85.416	36.776
Birth Order				
Only Child	240	60.75	85.417	36.69
First Born	63	15.94	86.100	36.87
Second Born	74	18.73	86.140	37.03
Third Born	9	2.27	87.695	37.50

Twins	22	5.56	86.246	36.85
Comorbidity				
Yes	159	40.26	86.283	36.68
No	236	59.74	85.436	36.616

Comorbidity

Table: showing percentage of Comorbidity

SOCIAL RESPONSIVE SCALE

Table

Table below shows scores of domains of Social Responsiveness Scale

Domains of Social Responsiveness Scale				
Symptom domains	(n)	%	Mean	SD
Social Awareness				

Normal	237	60	8.244	3.89
Mild	50	12.65	8.207	3.871
Moderate	60	15.18	8.241	3.887
Severe	42	10.63	8.194	3.853
Social Cognition				
Normal	224	56.70	13.211	6.044
Mild	79	20	13.196	6.067
Moderate	61	15.44	25.239	9.864
Severe	34	8.60	13.241	6.120
Social Communication				
Normal	190	48.10	23.242	9.005
Mild	63	15.94	23.260	8.978
Moderate	86	21.77	23.382	9.080
Severe	57	14.43	23.333	9.111
Social Motivation				
Normal	212	53.67	13.334	5.542
Mild	79	20	13.436	5.593
Moderate	60	15.18	13.379	5.546
Severe	45	11.39	13.382	5.550
Restricted and Repetitive Behaviour				
Normal	175	44.30	15.420	6.408
Mild	71	17.97	15.464	6.492
Moderate	95	24.05	15.383	6.461

Severe	54	13.67	15.420	6.444
Social Communication Index				
Normal	179	45.31	56.590	20.265
Mild	86	21.77	56.850	20.306
Moderate	89	22.53	56.850	20.380
Severe	41	10.37	56.850	20.490

RESULTS OF SRS

It was seen that 40.26 percent of children surveyed had comorbid conditions, apart from ASD. It was seen that in the Social Awareness Domain of the SRS, 15.18 % of the survey children were from the Moderate category. In the Social Cognition Domain of the SRS, 20 % of the survey children were from the Mild category. In the Restricted and Repetitive Behaviour Domain of the SRS, 24 % of the survey children were from the Moderate category. In the Social Communication Index Domain of the SRS, 22 % of the survey children were from the Moderate category.

SOCIAL INCLUSION AND SUPPORT SURVEY

Category	(n)	%	Mean age	SD
Inclusion				
Yes	271	68.60	85.349	37.733
No	124	31.39	85.807	36.673
Pull Out Therapy				
Yes	53	13.41	85.349	36.714
No	342	86.58	85.349	37.142

Post School Therapy				
Yes	190	48.1	86.282	36.505
No	205	51.9	86.349	36.690
Social Skill Program				
Yes	53	13.41	85.349	37.33
No	342	86.58	85.349	37.142
Factors affecting inclusion				
Behaviour of the Child	143	36.2	-	-
Speech of the child	97	24.6	-	-
Social Skills of the Child	98	24.8	-	-
Academic Skills Of the Child	12	3.0	-	-
Self Help Skills of the child	4	1.0	-	-
Attention Skills Of the Child	41	10.4	-	-

Inclusion

Table: showing percentage of Inclusion

Pull Out Therapy

Table: showing percentage of Pull Out Therapy

Post School Therapy

Table: showing percentage of Post School Therapy

Social Skills Program

Table: showing percentage of Social Skills Program

Factors Affecting Inclusion

Table: showing percentage of Factors Affecting Inclusion

Percentage of Factors

Table: showing percentage of Factors Affecting Inclusion

RESULTS OF SURVEY

The research showed that almost 30 percent of the children surveyed were not a part of an inclusive educational setting.

It was seen that 86 percent of the children surveyed were not receiving any pull out therapy in school.

48 percent of the children were seen to be receiving post school therapy, meaning that over 50 percent of children did not receive any kind of additional therapy apart from regular schooling which may or may not have been inclusive.

In terms of Social Skills Program, only 13 percent were receiving such programs, and the majority of the surveyed population was not getting trained in any type of social skills, which children with Autism majorly lack.

When asked about what factors affects the inclusion of ASD children in educational settings, the majority of 36 percent mentioned it was the behavior of the child, followed by similar percentages of Social skills and Speech with 24.8% and 24.6% respectively.

Inferential Statistics

Correlation between Age and SRS

Pearson correlation (r) test was performed to understand the significance of correlation between Social Inclusion and age of children. The correlation coefficient was generated with different domains Awareness ($r = 0.34$), Social cognition ($r = 0.90$), Social Communication ($r=0.59$), Social Motivation ($r = 0.57$), Restricted Repetitive Behaviour ($r = 0.37$), Total score ($r=0.16$) and Social Communication Index ($r=0.42$) were found to be statistically insignificant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Comparison of Male and female scores

The researcher hypothesised that the mean of scores of Male and Female children with Autism in terms of their severity scores are different. The Independent t test was selected and the results of an independent sample t test failed to support the hypothesis that “The score of Social Responsiveness is different for male and female children.” As the statistical analysis was found to be insignificant for all the symptom domains of SRS scale.

Comparison of the differences of mean scores of ASD children with inclusive settings

The researcher hypothesised that the mean of scores of inclusive settings i.e children who did attend inclusive settings and child who did not attend have different scores in different symptom domains

of SRS scale. The mean value of total severity score of children who said yes to inclusion was 1.94, (SD= 1.015); $t = -0.501$, $p > 0.05$ was not significantly different from mean value of raw severity score of children who said no to inclusion was 2.28, (SD=1.186). The results of an independent sample t test failed to support the hypothesis that “The score of Social Responsiveness is different for children who attended and did not attend inclusive education.” As the statistical analysis was found to be insignificant for all the symptom domains of SRS scale.

Comparison of the scores of ASD children who attended social skills training program with whom did not

The Independent t test was selected to find out if the scores of symptom domains of SRS was different for children receiving social skills training or not. The mean value of severity score of children who said yes to social skills program was 1.75, (SD=0.853) ; $t = -3.953$, $p < 0.05$ was significantly different from mean value of severity score of children who said no to social skills program was 2.10, (SD= 1.114). The results of an independent sample t test has partially supported the hypothesis that “The score of severity score is significantly different for those who received social skills training programs for different symptom domains of SRS scale.” The symptom domains which were significantly different were, Social Communication symptom domain, Social Cognition symptom domain and Restricted Repetitive Behaviour symptom domain.

Table below shows the distribution of scores.

Independent t test - Children who did and did not attend social skills training program						
	Attended social skills program	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t value	Remarks
	Yes	53	1.66	.939	-1.192	Not Significant

Awareness severity Score	No	34 2	1.80	1.092		
Social Cognition Severity Score	Yes	53	1.74	.984	-2.844	Significant
	No	34 2	1.75	.995		
Social Communication Severity Score	Yes	53	1.96	1.018	-2.102	Significant
	No	34 2	2.03	1.147		
Social Motivation Severity Score	Yes	53	1.83	1.014	-1.148	Not Significant
	No	34 2	1.85	1.068		
Restricted Repetitive Behavior Severity Score	Yes	53	2.15	1.167	-3.953	Significant
	No	34 2	2.06	1.100		
	Yes	53	1.75	.853	-2.970	Significant

RAW severity score	No	34	2.10	1.114		
		2				
Social Communication Index Severity Score	Yes	53	1.77	.891	-1.969	Not Significant
	No	34	2.01	1.067		
		2				

Table: showing comparison of the difference of mean scores of Social Responsiveness scale of those children who attended social skills program with those that have not attended

Discussion

The overall sample was first characterised using descriptive statistics. Descriptive statistics help us understand and summarise the data organising characteristics of a data set.

Although the population of students with ASD is characterised by heterogeneity and different levels of social adaptation, there is no clear picture of the importance and influence that the specific variables mentioned above have in social skills of students with ASD (Syriopoulou-Delli et al., 2016). The core objective of this study was to understand the differences in social skills among children with autism spectrum disorder (ASD). In order to investigate these differences, social skills were associated with characteristics of these children like age and then, on the basis of these results, to be able to predict the abilities and the difficulties of social skills of our future students, in order to create the most appropriate programs and interventions for them.

Therefore, according to the parent’s ratings obtained in the context of the present study, the study attempted to determine whether characteristics of ASD children was a variable that differentiated the level of social abilities. The participants were asked to specify the gender of their kids. The

frequency was computed to compare the number of males and females. The sample shows that the number of males was higher than the number of females in the sample collected. Halladay et al, 2015 and Wing 1981b also found that the prevalence of males was more than girls diagnosed with autism spectrum disorder (ASD). Similar results have been suggested by other studies that there are no gender differences in core features of autism (Holtmann et al., 2007; Pilowsky et al., 1998; Solomon et al., 2011; Tsai & Beisler, 1983).

The mean age (in months) of the children based on their gender identification was 85.34 for males and 85.8 for females in the sample which implies that the sample was homogenous. Another study (Syriopoulou-Delli et al., 2016) which analysed social skills factors with gender of ASD children found that there were no significant differences in the mean between the girls and the boys. The results of their study showed no population mean differences in the factors concerning gender which matches this study's results also.

Analysis of age (in months) and their scores on the different domains of social responsiveness wherein the age reported by the parents. The highest age range of the children in this study was 60 - 90 with n= 143. The lowest range of the children was 150 - 180 with n=16 and with a wide range of samples, more implications can be determined.

The level of education received by the children was also a homogenous sample in their mean age as the highest distribution for school grade level was found in the pre-school group was 23345 and followed by school 86.473 and non attending group 85.416. The frequency of single/ only children were reported to be the highest n=240 (60.75%) followed by second born n=74(18.73%); then second born with n=63 (15.94%) then twins with n=22(5.56%) and third born with the lowest n=9 (2.27%). This study determined the percentage of children who had comorbid conditions as reported by their parents. 59.74% of children reported for non-comorbid conditions and 40.26% reported for comorbid conditions. The relationship between the severity of ASD and the factors influencing social inclusion in the level of ASD children wherein the level of severity on the normal range was 43.03%, followed by mild and moderate range 21.77% for both and 13.41% for the severe range.

A correlation test was done to explore the association between age and Social skills in children. It was found that children with autism do not correlate in their Social Responsiveness symptom

domains and their age. The severity of symptoms does not reduce with increasing age or vice versa. In line with the results of the current study, (Linnenbank et al., 2021), suggested that school children with ASD should be entitled to special assistance and compensation in educational settings independent of their age, symptom severity. Some studies (Weitlauf et al., 2014, Bernier, 2012) have also argued that DSM-5 ASD severity differentiations are unclear and severity differentiations may change according to age and developmental level or how they will impact individuals' eligibility for and access to services across systems of care. On the other hand, Syriopoulou-Delli et al. in 2016 suggested that the results of their study showed that the older age group (12–17 years old) had better social skills instead of the younger age group (6–11 years old) which could be because of many reasons. One of them could be that as children grow up, they enrol in more activities and get exposed to more social skills which younger children can't.

When social skills were calculated with SRS scale scores the results of an independent sample t test, it partially supported the hypothesis that “The score of severity score is significantly different for those who received social skills training programs for different symptom domains of SRS scale.” The symptom domains which were significantly different were, social communication social cognition and RRB. The severity score was also significantly different for children who attended social skills programmes and children who did not. Hence, it can be concluded that social skills therapy helps children in their social behaviour. Social Training groups provide a structured environment to learn and practice social skills with peers (Laugeson et al. 2009).

On an overall sample, according to this study, it was seen that even though the sample was collected from parents who's children were diagnosed with ASD via medical practitioner, 170 children reported normal severity scores on SRS scales which indicates that the children did not have any symptom of ASD. Hence, it can be concluded that SRS-like self report questionnaires are not suitable for India in ASD children because parents tend to provide biased answers. As a result, it is suggested for future studies to take specific measures before doing any kind of study with neurodiverse children.

The results of an independent sample t test failed to support the hypothesis that “The score of Social Responsiveness is different for children who attended and did not attend inclusive education.” As the statistical analysis was found to be insignificant for all the symptom domains of SRS scale. Meaning that social skills training has a significant impact on children with ASD.

Conclusion

The results of the current study found that children with autism who attended and who did not attend inclusion classes have the almost same level of social responsiveness symptom domains of Social Responsiveness Scale. This implies that the study suggests that there is no difference in the SRS scale symptom domains if the child attends or does not attend Inclusive settings.

The results of an independent sample t test has supported the hypothesis that “*The score of social cognition is different for children with social skills program*”. Thus, it can be concluded that both groups who attended and did not attend inclusion classes have significant differences in scores for the social cognition symptom domain of Social Responsiveness Scale. Proponents of social skills training programs like Jones and Frederickson (2010) study, suggest that schools should be more confident in implementing generic social skills programmes, which normally focus on the development of cooperative behaviors that can help children more by improving social acceptance (Bauminger 2002) and effective inclusion.

Thus the study proves that there is a significant impact of social skills training in children with ASD, which can be seen on the Social Responsiveness Scale.

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